

1 **Title:** An automated low-cost solution for creating a multiple-step thermal gradient to record daily
2 fish thermoregulatory behaviour.

3

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18 **Supplementary Information**

19 **1. Temperature gradient multi-chamber tank system**

20 We built three 108 L multi-chamber glass tanks (180 × 30 × 20 cm) internally divided into
21 seven interconnected chambers. The two lateral chambers are used only for filtering the water (Magic
22 filter 50, Prodac, Italy), while the remaining five housed the fish (Fig. S1). Each chamber (30 × 30 ×
23 20 cm) is separated from the others by black non-toxic polyvinyl chloride (PVC) panels which has a
24 hole (Ø 5 cm; heigh 12 cm from the bottom of the tank) positioned in the middle to allow fish passage.
25 This set up resembled a semi-natural condition in which fish can freely move and choose among
26 different thermal environments across the day (see for similar system).¹⁻⁴ The system was placed in a
27 constant darkness room maintained at a temperature of 28 ± 1 °C by air condition system (Vitoclima
28 300-S, Viessmann, Germany).

29 **Figure S1.** Photo of the three multi-chamber glass tanks built for investigating daily variation of
30 thermal preference in fish. Each chamber is equipped with a mini water pump (green arrow), a
31 thermostat resistance heater (yellow arrow) and a temperature probe (red arrow). In the right-extreme
32 chambers of each multi-chamber tank (white asterisk), there is a steel coils through which cooled
33 water flow, while a filter was positioned in the left-extreme chambers (white cross).
34

35

36 Each chamber was equipped with i) a water pump (SunSun HJ-311, China), which prevent
37 the creation of a vertical temperature gradient and oxygenate the water; ii) a thermostat resistance
38 heater (AquaHeat 50, Juwel Aquarium, Germany) and iii) a water-proof probe (Ds18b20, AZ-
39 Delivery Vertriebs GmbH, Germany), which constantly measure the temperature (Figure S1). The
40 lowest temperature of 24 °C was guaranteed by the thermal exchange of cooled water passing
41 through a steel coil immersed in the lateral compartment of the multi-chamber tank. The water
42 inside the steel coil was maintained within a closed circuit connected to an external chiller (Tk 500,
43 Teco Srl, Italy). By maintaining a constant temperature in the experimental room where the system
44 is placed, the minimum and maximum range of temperature can reach 16 °C and 34 °C.

45 A custom-made infrared lamp (141.5 × 18 × 4 cm; Fig. S2) covered with translucent acrylic
46 white sheet (Falken Design WT2447-1-8/2436 Acrylic White Sheet, Translucent 55%, 152 × 26 ×
47 0.2 cm) was placed on the back of each multi-chamber tank for videorecording in the dark
48 condition.

49

50 **Figure S2.** Photo and representative diagram of the circuit used to create infrared LED lamp. Each
51 lamp presented 5 panel connected in series, where each panel consist in 50 Infrared LED (938-942 λ ;
52 Forward Voltage 1.15-1.20; Superlight, Elcart Distribution S.p.A., Italy; see the list of components).
53 Each panel consisted of 5 lines of 6-leds in parallel wiring and 4 lines of 5-leds in parallel wiring.
54 The 9 lines were connected in series wiring.

55

56 **2. Automated temperature controller and videorecording system**

57 A microcontroller board compatible with Arduino IDE (Elegoo Mega R3, Elegoo, China) was
58 used to automatically create and maintain the horizontal thermal gradient in the multi-chamber tank
59 (Fig. S3).

60

61 **Figure S3.** Arduino-based microcontroller circuit built to create the horizontal thermal gradient in
62 the multi-chamber tank.

63

64 The microcontroller continuously read data from the temperature probe every 5 mins and
 65 recorded the information in a microSD memory (SanDisk Ultra 32 GB, Milpitas, USA). The time of
 66 recording was provided from a RTC Clock module (DS3231, AZ-Delivery Vertriebs GmbH,
 67 Germany) and the acquired information was stored in the microSD (Fig. S4).

68

69 **Figure S4.** (A) Example of recorded temperature saved in .txt file. The first column (light blue)
 70 reported the date, the second column (green) the time of recording, the remaining columns
 71 represented the temperature from the hotter chamber (3rd column, 32 °C, yellow column) to the cooler
 72 chamber (7th column, 24 °C, purple column). Each column is separated by coma. (B) Hourly
 73 temperature stability for each chamber recorded across 6 days. Data points represent mean \pm
 74 standard error of hourly temperatures recorded every 5 minutes. The arrow indicated the moment in
 75 which the recording was interrupted, and the multi-chamber tank was refilled. After few hours, the
 76 temperature returned to the pre-set range for each chamber. (C) Thermal images of the multi-chamber
 77 tank using a FLIR E54 Thermal Imaging Camera (Teledyne FLIR LLC, Oregon, USA). Image
 78 showed the horizontal thermal gradient from 32 °C (yellow) to 24 °C (purple) generated and
 79 maintained by the microcontroller. The vertical temperature was equal between the bottom and the
 80 top of each tank.

81

82 Once the microcontroller recorded the temperature from each temperature probe, the
83 information was projected from a 16 × 2 LCD Display (HD44780, AZ-Delivery Vertriebs GmbH,
84 Germany), then the microcontroller switched on/off the single heater in each chamber depending on
85 the settled temperature threshold as described in the following flowchart (Fig. S5).

86

87 **Figure S5.** Flowchart of the algorithm developed for creating and controlling the thermal
88 gradient in the multi-chambered tank.

89

90 Since the thermostat resistance heater required high-voltage electric current (220 v), the relay
91 circuit was designed to be always open/disconnected, i.e. sending power to the heaters is constrained
92 to the activation of microcontroller and whether acquired temperature information from the probe is
93 below the pre-setted threshold.

94 The microcontroller is programmed using Arduino IDE (Integrated Development
95 Environment), a user-friendly open-source software development platform. We created a custom
96 program (Fig. S5) where it was possible to define several parameters, such as the temperature in each
97 chamber and the range of temperature tolerance for switch on/off the heater as well as the latency
98 between recording time point.

99 The Arduino code can be downloaded from
100 <https://github.com/CristianoBertolucci/FishTemperatureGradientSystem>.

101

102 To assess daily thermal preference, fish behaviour was recorded by using three different
103 camera modules, placed at 170 cm from the tanks, connected each to a Raspberry Pi (Raspberry Pi 4
104 model B, Raspberry Pi, UK). Videorecording is performed by a custom written Python script (Fig.
105 S6) based on picamera package (ver. 1.13), which provided a flexible solution for the collection of
106 long-term recording of good quality (i.e., 2 hours of continuously recording are 240 MB)⁵. For an
107 updated version of the package, which results depreciable for the new O.S. (Linux version \geq 11) and
108 Kernel (version \geq 6.6.1), the experiment considered using Picamera2 library
109 (<https://datasheets.raspberrypi.com/camera/picamera2-manual.pdf>). We used Tkinter to create a user-
110 friendly GUI for the application (<https://docs.python.org/3/library/tkinter.html>).

111

112

113 **Figure S6.** (A) The video recording software used to prolong record fish behaviour. (B) Photo of
 114 video recording in the condition of light on and (C) darkness during the night.

115

116 We reported the parameters that the users can modify to increase image quality according to the
 117 light condition and settings:

- 118 • *Number of Video Recordings*: user defined the number of video recording to be generated
 119 according to the duration of the experiment.
- 120 • *Recordings hours per video*: users defined the number of hours per each video recording.
- 121 • *FPS* (framerate per second): defined the number of frames the camera could capture per
 122 second. Because the experiments required longer recordings, we suggested to set up to 1 frame
 123 per seconds.
- 124 • *Shutter Speed* (“shutter_speed” parameter): define the exposure attribute (length of time) that
 125 the camera is exposed to light (e.g., the time at which point the captured scene would become
 126 blurry). The time was expressed in microseconds. We suggested to increase this parameter
 127 when observing high-active fish and/or low light intensity condition.
- 128 • *Sensor Mode* (“sensor_mode” parameter): defined the resolutions of video recordings.
 129 According to the FPS (1) and shutter speed (35-50 ms) parameters and the position camera

130 from the tank (180 cm), we usually set to 2, corresponding to 3280 × 2464 resolution and 4:3
131 aspect ratio.

- 132 • *Select save folder*: defined the path where the video recordings would be saved.

133 To increase the final quality of recordings, experimenters might consider acquiring multiple
134 images rather than a continuously recording because more parameters might be implemented, such
135 as brightness and light contrast. We suggested to look at the documentation of the library for setting
136 the parameters according to the experimental condition ([https://picamera.readthedocs.io/en/release-
137 1.13/fov.html](https://picamera.readthedocs.io/en/release-1.13/fov.html)).

138 Once recording started, the application generated a short video called “*trash*” (duration 15-
139 sec). This was necessary because the camera module required a short loading-time to set up the
140 recording parameters defined by the user. Then, the application generated a user-defined number of
141 videos of the chosen duration, which were identified by a sequential number, e.g. "0Video", "1Video".
142 The format of the videos was H.264, which could be covert to other type of format code. To further
143 reduce the disturbance and limiting the entrance to the experimental room, we remotely controlled
144 the Raspberry Pi by using Virtual Network Computing (VNC) app, such as RealVNC® server
145 (<https://www.realvnc.com/en/>).

146 The source code for video recording and the information to execute the code can be
147 downloaded from <https://github.com/CristianoBertolucci/FishTemperatureGradientSystem>.

148

149 We designed the system in the optic of acquiring automatically long-term data with the
150 minimum of components, which are low cost and easily reachable from common marketplaces.⁶
151 Although there is several commercial equipment that allows researchers to record the behavior of
152 fish, we preferred to build our system by assembling separated components that might be easily
153 adjusted according to experimental conditions and quickly substitute in case of
154 necessity/maintenance. For example, the infrared LED lamp might be substituted with commercial

155 lamp or, alternatively, several module cameras designed for Raspberry Pi are provided with light-
 156 sensitive infrared light.

157 The list of components is reported below (reference price acquired on October 31st 2024 from
 158 amazon.com):

Quantity	Component	Description & Cost
<i>Automated temperature controller</i> (total cost: 157.88\$ – 191.21\$)		
1	ATmega2560 micro-controller board	<p>A microcontroller board based on the ATmega2560 used to automatically control the system. The choice of using an ATmega2560 board is mainly related to the elevated number of digital input/output pins (54) necessary for controlling all the electronic components of the system. The experiment may consider alternative solutions for smaller-size (i.e., ATmega328P provided with 14 pins) and/or cheaper (i.e., Arduino, Elegoo) board.</p> <p>Average cost for Arduino Mega R3: 53.00\$</p> <p>Average cost for Arduino Uno R3: 27.60\$</p> <p>Average cost for Elegoo Mega R3: 21.99\$</p> <p>Average cost for Elegoo Uno R3: 16.99\$</p>
1	Real Time Clock (RTC) module compatible with DS3231	<p>Maintain accurate timekeeping.</p> <p>Average cost per two units: 5.99\$</p>
1	MicroSD Card Reader Module Adapter SPI Interface	<p>Store the red temperature and time for further checking of the thermal gradient stability across days.</p> <p>Average cost per two units: 5.99\$</p>
1	LCD I2C 16x2	<p>Display the temperature read from each probe</p> <p>Average cost per two units plus adapter: 9.99\$ - 11.99\$</p>
2	400-pins Breadboard	Build the circuit (see scheme Fig. S2)
	jumper and solid wire	Average cost per unit including of multiple wires: 16.99\$
1	4-channel relay 5V	<p>The relay shield provided an easy way to control high-voltage devices, e.g. the 200-V heater.</p> <p>Average cost per one 4-channel relay unit: 7.99\$</p>

5	Water-Proof temperature probe (Ds18b20)	Read the water temperature in a specific compartment. Average cost per five units: 9.99\$ -11.99\$
4	thermostat resistance heater	Once read the temperature, the micro-controller board switch ON/OFF the heater via the relay according to the desired temperature threshold (Fig. S5). By changing the type of heater, the system might be potential applied for creating a horizontal thermal gradient in terrestrial cage. Average cost per one unit: 6.99\$ -14.32\$
1	USB A to USB B Cable	Connect the micro-controller board to a PC for uploading the source code. Average cost per one unit: 3.98\$ - 6.98\$
1	30W AC-to-DC adapter	External power supply for the micro-controller board setting up 9V. Average cost per one unit: 12.99\$
7	Resistor ¼ W	N = 5 resistor 4.7k $\Omega \pm 5\%$, one resistor connected to the input cable of each temperature probe. N = 1 resistor 330 $\Omega \pm 5\%$ wired to the Micro SD adapter. Average cost per unit including of multiple resistors: 12.99\$ - 20.99\$
	Junction box containing the microcontroller board and the circuit + material of stinning	Average cost: 10.99\$ - 18.99\$
<i>Videorecording system</i> (total cost: 82.98\$ – 138.92\$)		
1	Raspberry Pi 4 Model b + 32GB MicroSD for mounting the system. Operating System: Raspbian GNU/Linux 11 (bullseye). https://www.raspberrypi.com/software/operating-systems/ Kernel: Linux 6.1.21-v8+ Architecture: arm64	A custom-made code based on picamera library was used to long-exposition record fish behaviour by running on a Raspberry Pi 4 Module b Average cost per base-kit Raspberry Pi 4 Model b: 60\$ -110\$* Average cost per module Camera: 15.99\$ Average cost per flat Camera Cable: 6.99\$ *The custom-made software used for controlling the recording is based on the librabry piCamera. Previous model of Raspberry Pi (i.e. model 3) supported the library. On the contrary, piCamera library is

1	Power Supply (5.1V – 3A)	absolute for the latests version of Rspberry PI OS, thus the software necessarily requires the use of alternative library such as libcamera. https://git.linuxtv.org/libcamera.git/
1	5-MP RPi IR-CUT module Camera for supporting night vision.	
1	Flat Camera Cable (1 m)	
<i>Infrared LED lamp</i> <i>(the quantity of component refers to a single panel)</i>		
9	Resistor 2 W	N = 5 resistor 120 $\Omega \pm 5\%$, one resistor connected to the 6-led parallel lines input. N = 4 resistor 100 $\Omega \pm 5\%$, one resistor connected to the 5-led parallel lines input. Average cost per unit: 0.30\$
50	LED (938-942 λ ; Forward Voltage 1.15-1.20)	Average cost per unit: 0.07 \$
	Matrix board + material of stinning + plastic material for covering the lamp.	Average cost: 10\$

159

160 3. Experimental protocol

161 To validate our system, we investigated thermal preference of the teleost model zebrafish
162 *Danio rerio*. Adult zebrafish (n=36), derived from a wild-type strain descendant bought from a local
163 shop and maintained at the facility of University of Ferrara (Italy) since 2011, were kept in 230 L
164 glass tanks composed of mixed-sex groups. The aquaria were provided with mechanical, chemical,
165 and biological filters and water temperature was set at 27 ± 1 °C; water conductivity was maintained
166 at < 500 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, NO_2^- at < 0.1 mg/L and NO_3^- at < 25 mg/L. The fish were maintained under a LD
167 14:10 h (light/dark cycle) and were daily fed three times with live *Artemia salina* nauplii (*Artemia*
168 *Salina* Premium GLS, Belgium) and commercial dry flake food (Vipan Nature, Sera, Germany).

169 The sample size was chosen according to the UE recommendations to guarantee animal welfare
170 (2010/63/UE), establishing a maximum density of 1 fish/L. In the present experiment fish density
171 was 12 fish/18 L (1.5L per fish), a threshold kept below the UE recommendations to avoid stress and
172 negative effects on fish behaviour as in previous studies.^{2,3}

173 The experimental subjects were randomly selected from breeding stock. Each subject was
174 tested only once and released at the end of experiment for breeding and reproduction purpose;
175 therefore, the data of the different experiments and multi-chamber tanks were independent. Three
176 groups of zebrafish (n=12/group) were used. A continuous thermal gradient, from 24 °C to 32 °C,
177 was designed and create according to the physiology of the species.⁷ During the experiment, fish were
178 kept under a LD 14:10 h that was provided by a LED strip (light intensity 730 lux, TMR, ELCART,
179 Italy) placed 15 cm above each tank. Fish were fed *ad libitum* with *Artemia salina* live nauplii once
180 per day. Food was randomly administered during the day to avoid feeding entrainment.⁸⁻¹⁰ Excluding
181 the first day of recording for acclimatization, the video recording of each group lasted at least four
182 complete days.

183 4. Video Analysis

184 Processing of videos *in situ* motion detection is time and memory consuming for the limited
185 hardware of Raspberry Pi, consequently the analysis of the videos was successively performed using
186 the EthoVision XT tracking software (Noldus Information Technology, The Netherlands). The
187 software can track fish across days to obtain i) the cumulative time spent for each chamber from a
188 single tank and ii) the average quantification of locomotor activity of fish in the group. To increase
189 the performance of the software, tracked position of fish were weighted for 5 frames/second.

190 To verify the quality of the tracking, a blind experimenter performed a manual count of the
191 fish. By using a free multimedia player (VLC, VideoLAN, France), the experimenter extracted 1
192 frame every 5 minutes of real time recording. The frame ratio may vary depending on the operating
193 system, so we recommend checking the parameters to be reported for frame extraction. For example,

194 using Windows and VLC media player, the videos lasted 4 minutes (corresponding to 2-hour
195 recordings), we set 1 frame every 300 frames and obtained a total of 12 images/h. Then, the blind
196 experimenter counted manually the number of fish in each chamber of the system to calculate the
197 inter-rater reliability of the measure of thermal preference (total number of counted hours: 70). The
198 reliability test showed a strong correlation between the manual scores and the output from the tracking
199 software (Pearson's $r = 0.822$, $t_{68} = 11.918$, $P < 0.001$), highly supporting the use of automated
200 tracking system for quantifying average thermal preference and distance covered across tank of the
201 fish groups.

202 **5. Data and statistical analysis**

203 The statistical analysis for daily thermal preference and locomotor activity were performed in
204 RStudio version 2022.02.3 Build 492 (Integrated Development for R. RStudio, PBC, Boston, MA,
205 USA; <http://www.rstudio.com/>). The statistical tests were two-tailed, and significance threshold was
206 set at $P = 0.05$.

207 We initially performed a repeated measures analysis for evaluating differences on the thermal
208 preference and distance covered across the ZT. We analysed each behavioural parameter via Linear
209 Mixed Model (*lmer* function from *lme4* R package) fitted with ZT as numerical covariate for
210 accounting temporal fluctuation of interested behavioural parameter across day, Day as random factor
211 to account for the repeated measures structures of data. Significance of the models' parameters was
212 assessed via Satterhwaite's degrees of freedom (*anova* function from the *lmerTest* R package).
213 Both fitted models reveal a significant effect of ZT ("thermal preference" model: $F_{1,108} = 203.450$, P
214 < 0.001 ; "distance covered" model: $F_{1,108} = 109.090$, $P < 0.001$), suggesting the presence of daily
215 rhythm.

216 The possible existence of daily and circadian periodicity was determined by means of Cosinor
217 method.^{11,12} Briefly, the method assumed that circadian rhythms can defined as smooth rhythms

218 defined by parameters that could be estimate by fitting a least squares model consisting of cosine
 219 curves with known periods (24 h):

$$220 \quad y = M + A \cos\left(\frac{2\pi t}{\tau} + \phi\right) + e(t)$$

221 Where M is the MESOR (Midline Estimating Statistic of Rhythm), A is the amplitude of the
 222 oscillation (a measure of the extent between the Mesor and the peak of predictable variation within a
 223 cycle), t is standardizing time points expressed in *Zeitgeber* (synchronizer) time (ZT)¹³, ϕ is the
 224 Acrophase (a measure of the time in a cycle that the predictable variation reached the peak), τ is the
 225 period (duration of one cycle), and $e(t)$ is the error term. Assuming that the τ is known (24-hours),
 226 the equation could be arithmetically estimating by least squares linear regression:

$$227 \quad y \sim \text{intercept} + \sin\left(\frac{2\pi t}{24}\right) + \cos\left(\frac{2\pi t}{24}\right) + e(t)$$

228 The intercept of linear regression equals to the Mesor, i.e. the arithmetic means of all data
 229 points, while the Amplitude and the Acrophase can be calculated as following:

$$230 \quad A = \sqrt{\beta_{sin}^2 + \beta_{cos}^2}$$

$$231 \quad \phi = -\tan\frac{\beta_{sin}}{\beta_{cos}} \text{ when } \beta_{sin} > 0 \text{ and } \beta_{cos} \geq 0 \text{ or}$$

$$232 \quad = -\frac{\pi}{2} - \tan\frac{\beta_{sin}}{\beta_{cos}} \text{ when } \beta_{sin} \geq 0 \text{ and } \beta_{cos} < 0 \text{ or}$$

$$233 \quad = -\pi - \tan\frac{\beta_{sin}}{\beta_{cos}} \text{ when } \beta_{sin} < 0 \text{ and } \beta_{cos} \leq 0 \text{ or}$$

$$234 \quad = -\frac{3}{2}\pi - \tan\frac{\beta_{sin}}{\beta_{cos}} \text{ when } \beta_{sin} \leq 0 \text{ and } \beta_{cos} > 0 \text{ or}$$

235 The negative sign. “-” identified the clockwise direction of vector in the circular analysis. The
 236 existence of rhythmicity within the circle, i.e. the probability that the Amplitude is significantly

237 different from zero, can be assessed by calculating the F distribution with 2 and N-3 degrees of
238 freedom from the predicting value of linear regression. As reported in the Table S1, each group
239 showed a daily rhythmicity on the preferred temperature and distance covered across the multi-tank
240 system.

241 Due to the presence of significant rhythmicity in all 3 systems, we pooled the data (i.e, average
242 parameters from the three systems for each ZT across the five days) and performed the Cosinor
243 analysis on the new datasets as previously described.

244 In R platform, “*cosinor*” and “*cosinor2*” package used the same analytical approach we
245 describe (<https://github.com/sachsmc/cosinor>), which allow the user to detect the presence of
246 rhythmicity in temporal data by using pre-defined function.¹⁴ However, those packages present some
247 limitation on including multiple covariates and/or considering random factors in their model.¹⁵ In
248 case the experimenters are interested in studying daily variations in thermal preference over an
249 extended period, i.e. greater than 10 days, we suggest including the independent variable “day” in the
250 final model for accounting the global effect of prolonged exposition to the apparatus in estimating the
251 circadian parameters. Considering the linear model previously described, the variable “day” should
252 be included as a polynomial covariate by using the ‘*poly()*’ function from the ‘*stats*’ R package. The
253 degree of polynomial will be selected based on model comparison, i.e. Akaike's information criterion.
254 We obtain similar results using non-linear gam models by fitting the model with
255 $\sim s(\text{elapsed_time}, \text{bs} = \text{“cr”}) + s(\text{ZT}, \text{by} = \text{Group}, \text{bs} = \text{“cc”})$, where “elapsed_time” identifies a continuous
256 numerical sequences from the first ZT of day 1 to the end of experiment, and “Group” identifies the
257 group of fish (for a better discussion on defining the smooth terms, see the ‘*mgcv*’ R package).¹⁶ The
258 gam models allow to estimate complex non-linear relationships between variables³, however, such
259 non-linear models are less interpretable compared to the classical linear model.¹⁷

260 **Ethical Approval**

261 Husbandry and experimental procedures were performed in accordance with European
262 Legislation for the Protection of Animals used for Scientific Purposes (Directive 2010/63/EU) and
263 the Italian (D.L. 26/2014) animal protection standards. Research was also approved by the University
264 of Ferrara Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee and the Italian Ministry of Health (auth.
265 num. CB/01-2019). General license for fish maintenance and breeding at the University of Ferrara:
266 29/2023-UT. No physical invasive manipulations were performed on the fish during the experiments
267 and no fish showed sign of distress. At the end of the experiments, all subjects were released into
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